

CREATION OF A TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING A DRUG USED FOR CORONARY HEART DISEASE BASED ON LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

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Annotation: Biologically active compounds (polyphenols, polysaccharides, polyunsaturated fatty acids, phytosteroids, etc.) are increasingly used in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. Often, a person receives these substances mainly from food, and they are called essential components of nutrition. Doctors of various specialties and nutritionists are paying more and more attention to them. Thanks to research in the field of biochemistry, physiology and immunology, their mechanisms of action have become known, which makes it possible to create and scientifically justify the use of drugs based on them both as medicines and as biologically active food additives (dietary supplements) and tea drinks for preventive and therapeutic purposes.

Keywords: prevention and treatment, critical analysis, medicinal herbs

Some of the listed substances are not synthesized in the body and are called irreplaceable, and the synthesis of others may be limited or disrupted by the pathological process. Compared with other biologically active substances, they participate in metabolic processes in the cells of many tissues, which is the reason for a significant variety of physiological effects of deficiencies of these substances. Therefore, additional intake of essential nutrition components in the treatment of diseases reduces the risk of complications and recurrence.

There is some information and practical observations about the use of medicinal

plants and preparations from them in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. This direction in medicine is gaining more and more supporters, especially among cardiologists, district doctors and specialists of medical and social rehabilitation centers.

Unfortunately, the erudition of doctors in the field of phytopharmacology is not always sufficient. In the course of pharmacology, medical students study a limited list of medicinal plants (belladonna, henbane, etc.), when studying clinical disciplines medicinal plants are mentioned in single universities, students do not have the opportunity to obtain systematic knowledge about phytotherapy as a method of medical activity. The future doctor gets acquainted with the anatomy of a frog, a fish, but he is poorly oriented in the herbal medicinal world, often cannot answer an elderly patient how to use chamomile or calendula flowers, motherwort grass in everyday conditions. Once, talking with the management of the Cardiology Center in Volgograd, one of the authors was surprised by the beautiful premises of the center. When the question came up about the possibility of using herbal remedies in their conditions, it was said that they had an idea only about valerian and lily of the valley. Unfortunately, medical officials have not heard about other plants that can be successfully used in therapeutic cardiology.

In order to reduce the information vacuum in the possibilities of combined use of chemotherapy drugs and herbal remedies, to increase the effectiveness of therapy for cardiovascular patients, to reduce side effects from long-term chemotherapy to these patients, this publication has been published.

The authors of the monograph are specialists with many years of practical experience. This book has a practical focus. It contains not only the latest information from other authors, but also data from their own observations, extracts from medical histories.

One of the main tasks of this book is to comprehend the past of domestic and foreign medicine, to interpret its vast experience, to determine the directions and

ways of development of phytotherapy of cardiac patients. To do this, it is necessary to give a reliable, objective picture of the past, based on a critical analysis of historical facts, theories and practical observations, errors and misconceptions.

Fulfilling the social order of the time, we must put at the service of modernity the rich historical experience of domestic phytotherapy in the field of cardiology.

Classic indications: accumulation of wind in the heart region, mental restlessness, drowsiness, dizziness, palpitations, insomnia, anxiety, chest and liver pain, trembling in the arms and legs.

Indications: arrhythmias, arterial hypertension, conduction disorders, atherosclerosis.

Composition:

- eagle tree – brings out the wind of the heart (arrhythmias);
- nutmeg – the wind of the heart, soothing;
- plum – eliminates fever and treats heart disease;
- bamboo – cooling, lung diseases, soothes bile;
- boswelia (incense);
- mirobalan hebula balances all three doshas, and also has a detoxifying effect, cleanses the blood;
- devyasil high – diseases of blood and wind, restores digestive heat;
- indian quiscalis – enhances digestion, detoxification;
- add sugar.

The composition of the collection in different sources may vary slightly, substitutes are often used.

In this recipe, the eagle tree is in the first place, which has the main therapeutic effect, nutmeg is an assistant. Both have warm properties. Plum, bamboo and frankincense are cool ingredients that eliminate heat. Mirobalan balances all three doshas, together with elecampane and quitclaims, cleanses, and improves digestion. Thus, the main action: balancing the wind, eliminating heat,

detoxification and digestive support. The recipe is balanced, since there are components of both warm and cool properties.

In addition, it should be noted that the successes of classical pharmacology gave a new impetus to the development of phytotherapy, allowed a new look at the physiological effect of medicinal herbs, their interaction with synthetic drugs. This made it possible to reduce the dosages of both medicinal herbs and synthetic drugs, while obtaining better results and significantly fewer complications and side effects.

The revival of interest in traditional medicine, covering the entire spectrum of plants, and not just those listed in the register, is due to several reasons.

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